

Expected Value of Uniswap v3 Liquidity Pools in an Arb-Only World

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Abstract

We analyze the expected value of deploying capital in a Uniswap v3 liquidity pool under arbitrage-only trading when the underlying asset price dynamics are given by an Euler-discretized Geometric Brownian Motion. Our main contribution is an accurate closed-form approximation for the expected value and expected trading volume. The formula illustrates a simple trade-off between expected loss and trading volume.

1 Liquidity Pools: A Brief History

The ideas behind Liquidity Pools (LP) pre-date blockchains ([4] [2]) but grew in popularity since they were a practical solution to enable on-chain exchanges in the computationally constrained environment of the Ethereum Blockchain ([3]). A popular implementation is Uniswap ([8]).

2 Our Setup

Suppose we are going to deposit some initial capital C into a Uniswap v3 ([8]) style liquidity pool (LP) for a token X - token Y pair for a period of T years. For simplicity we'll assume token Y is a US dollar denominated stablecoin since the most popular defi pools are the ETH and USD stablecoin pairs, but the arguments given here are more general. A Uniswap-v3 style pool requires specifying a lower and upper bound price, denoted by p_l and p_u respectively, as the liquidity range, along with a constant trading fee of f_l basis points.

There is only one type of trader interacting with our LP, an arbitrageur who will buy or sell whenever a minimum profit of f_a bps, relative to another external exchange which they consider the ground truth price, may be obtained. The arbitrageur can trade instantaneously and for unlimited size. This type of setup and similar has been analyzed before ([1] [5]).

2.1 Price Process

Trading decisions occur at some frequency of Δt seconds (e.g. 12 for Ethereum block frequency), at each time step $0, \Delta t, 2\Delta t, \dots, T$ the arbitrageur compares the LP and external prices and will make an instantaneous trading decision.

A standard discrete time asset price model used in financial options theory is discretized Geometric Brownian Motion ([6]). Our spot process for X in units of our stablecoin Y will be driven by:

$$\Delta \log S_t = (r - q - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2)\Delta t + \sigma\sqrt{\Delta t}\epsilon_i$$

Where ϵ_i are i.i.d random standard normals, r is the risk free interest rate, q is a continuous dividend (e.g. from staking), and σ is the asset volatility. In what follows we assume r and q are 0.

3 Internal Accounting

3.1 Hold a Simple Basket

At time $t = 0$, a Uniswap v3 LP contains some initial allocation of w_x units of token X , and w_s units of the stablecoin. Let B_t be the random variable corresponding to the value of this portfolio at time t , standard finance arguments give:

$$\mathbb{E}[B_T] = \mathbb{E}[w_x X_T - w_s S_T] = w_x X_0 - w_s S_0.$$

where \mathbb{E} is shorthand for the conditional expectation given information at time 0 (for details see [6]). In particular let's define revenue (a more accurate term would be PnL for profit and loss) of any investment as it's change in value, we can show the expected revenue of this investment is:

$$\mathbb{E}[B_T - B_0] = 0 \tag{1}$$

3.2 World Agents

We now reinterpret this same initial allocation in terms of internal accounts. From the outside world's perspective we're going to passively hold our initial basket, so the expected revenue remains zero. Internally, however, we're going to control two agents who may only trade with one another:

- A passive LP as describe above, whose initial weights must match those of basket B_0 .
- An arbitraging trader as described above.

While not considered, we could easily include other agents e.g. an explicit external exchange with its own fees for the scenario when the arbitrager will only trade whenever they can immediately offload their LP trades.

3.3 Expected Revenue

Let the random variables corresponding to the LP's and arbitrager's final revenue at time T be denoted by R_{lp} and R_a , respectively. Since these agents are our own internal accounting, their sum must match (1):

$$\mathbb{E}[R_{lp} + R_a] = 0 \tag{2}$$

It turns out we can derive good approximations for both R_{lp} and R_a , which depend on a single unknown, namely the expected volume. Proceeding, assume V dollars will trade on the LP in expectation.

3.3.1 Arbitrager Expected Revenue

At timestep i , the arbitrager executes a trade of size N_i , with external and LP prices denoted by S_i and P_i , respectively. The expected revenue from the arbitrager's trading is:

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=0} N_i \cdot (S_T - P_i) \right] = \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=0} N_i \cdot (S_T - S_i) \right] + \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i=0} N_i \cdot (S_i - P_i) \right]$$

The first term is 0 and the second term can be approximated:

$$\left(\frac{f_a}{10^4} + \epsilon \right) \cdot V \tag{3}$$

Since the arbitrager's revenue per trade is always at least f_a bps, but it may be significantly more if there is a favorably large $\Delta \log S_t$ move in a Δt time step. A heuristic argument leads us to claim that this excess revenue, the ϵ in (3), is linear in total volatility, fitting this model (see B) yields:

$$\mathbb{E}[R_a] \approx \left(\frac{f_a}{10^4} + \frac{1.0352}{10^4} \sigma \sqrt{\Delta t} \right) \cdot V \tag{4}$$

3.3.2 LP Expected Revenue

Recall that the Impermanent Loss (IL), is given as the loss of a Liquidity Pool’s asset value versus holding the initial basket B_0 (see [7] for more details). Note that our convention is that IL is a positive number, that it hurts liquidity providers is reflected in the “loss” part of the name. We can approximate our LP revenue as:

$$\mathbb{E}[R_{lp}] \approx \frac{f_{lp}}{10^4} \cdot V - \mathbb{E}[\text{IL}] \quad (5)$$

Let $p(x)$ be the terminal density of S_T , let $h(p)$ be our impermanent loss function for a final pool price p , then any reasonable numerical quadrature package can reliably compute:

$$\mathbb{E}[\text{IL}] \approx \int_0^\infty p(x)h(x) dx \quad (6)$$

If numerical stability is an issue then you may want to use the log-pdf. This is an approximation since we are not using the inventory as a function of the true more complicated LP spot price distribution.

3.3.3 Main Result

Putting (2) (4), (5) together we obtain our main result, the expected volume is given by:

$$V \approx \frac{\mathbb{E}[\text{IL}]}{f_{lp} + f_a + 1.0352 \cdot \sigma\sqrt{\Delta t}} \cdot 10^4 \quad (7)$$

Note that the denominator can be interpreted as the “total fees”. Finally, the expected value of our investment in the liquidity pool is:

$$\mathbb{E}[R_{lp}] \approx \left(\frac{f_{lp}}{f_{lp} + f_a + 1.0352 \cdot \sigma\sqrt{\Delta t}} - 1 \right) \mathbb{E}[\text{IL}] \quad (8)$$

Notice that (8) is strictly negative.

4 Monte Carlo Results

Our ultimate justification for (7) and (8) is by Monte Carlo simulation. By fitting our model to the simulation data, we obtain an r^2 greater than 99% (see B). Here we present some sample scenarios with the number of paths increased to 10,000:

Simulation Parameters							Results				
f_l	f_a	p_l	p_u	T	Δt	σ	MC EV	EV from (8)	z score	L	$\mathbb{E}[\text{IL}]$
5	1	0	∞	1/12	12	.9	-0.372 %	-0.385 %	1.01	1	0.84 %
5	1	150	170	2/12	.5	1.1	-1.223 %	-1.149 %	-0.43	49.5	4.33 %
5	1	30	50	2/12	.5	1.1	-0.115 %	-0.163 %	1.75	8.9	0.61 %
2	.5	110	110.01	1/12	1.0	.6	-1.191 %	-1.190 %	-0.02	48 k	3.31 %
5	1.5	80	120	1/12	.2	.4	-0.403 %	-0.425 %	0.92	10.4	1.68 %
50	1.5	80	120	1/12	.2	.4	-0.034 %	-0.055 %	0.87	10.4	1.68 %

Table 1: Monte Carlo simulation results for various scenarios. The initial token X price is always \$100.

The parameters were already introduced, the results sub-table compares the Monte Carlo estimated liquidity pool revenue in ‘MC EV’ against the result using (8). The z column divides their difference by the Monte Carlo standard error to obtain a z-score, which is always less than 2 in magnitude. The other columns are included for convenience, for leverage L see [8].

5 Concluding Thoughts

This type of analysis can be done for any discrete time martingale including those with jumps. The main challenge in using other price processes would be finding the right form for the arbitrageur’s total revenue given by (4).

Formula (7) demonstrates a simple trade-off between expected loss and volume. All the pool characteristics and complexity (besides trading fees f_{lp}) influence volume and expected revenue only through the $\mathbb{E}[\text{IL}]$ term. The only property of liquidity pools we relied on in our arguments was that the pool let’s an agent arbitrage it against a fair external market. This formula is very general, and applies to many other types automated market makers besides constant product market-makers.

The formula is primarily useful as a toy model to gain insight into liquidity provision. This toy model may help us get a sense how much Uniswap volume is actual retail trading in order to make a fairer comparison between DeFi and centralized exchange volumes.

While doing any real-world analysis of Uniswap trading should ultimately rely on actual trading and liquidity data, one loose practical application of this formula is to give a very rough idea what volume an arb-only pool will generate (though inexact because liquidity providers may be re-balancing). From that, one may determine how much non-arb volume a protocol receives.

Lastly, we mention the expected value of a liquidity pool investment in this arb-only world will always be negative, a fact not widely appreciated in the DeFi community. The simple argument given in 3 proves this since we can easily see $E[R_a] > 0$.

A Code

The code will be posted to GitHub shortly.

B Fitting Arbitrageur Excess Revenue

We ran 1000 random scenarios of LP’s generated by roughly the following Python code:

```
1 SimConfig(fee_pool_bps=np.random.uniform(0, 15),
2           min_edge_bps=np.random.uniform(0, 3),
3           price_asset_base=100,
4           pool_price_lo=np.random.uniform(0, 100),
5           pool_price_hi=np.random.uniform(100, 1000),
6           investment_base=1e6,
7           time_step_sec=np.random.uniform(0.01, 1 0)
8           sim_time_years=np.random.uniform(0, 3/12),
9           interest_rate=0.0,
10          volatility=np.random.uniform(0, 2))
```

Listing 1: Python simulation scenarios

After some data cleaning where 1.) remove simulations that barely traded and 2.) those where the MC and theoretical IL meaningfully disagreed. We regressed $\sigma\sqrt{\Delta t}$ on the excess arbitrageur revenue (that is the revenue in excess of f_a bps) and obtain a fit with r^2 over 99 %. We used a weighted least squares regression since we have Monte Carlo noise estimates on the excess revenue (this did not meaningfully change the results versus OLS).

The final fit coefficient on the $\sigma\sqrt{\Delta t}$ term was 1.0352 with a 95% confidence interval of ± 0.00056 .

Here we plot the MC Volume versus (7) differences, along with the ± 2 standard error bars, inspecting the worst offenders we see that the theoretical IL from (6) meaningfully differs from the MC estimate. These points were excluded, as part of our data cleaning described in the preceding paragraph, as the culprit could be a faulty numerical integration since they all had $\sigma^2 T$ near the top of the simulation range.

Figure 1: Predicted versus Equation (7) Volume, along with 2 std error bars

References

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